

The Application of Rigorous Numerical Methods for Analyzing Heterogeneous Geospatial Data

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Abstract. This study addresses the analysis of heterogeneous geospatial data through the application of rigorous numerical methods in cartometric, geodetic, and morphometric operations. The research focuses on improving the accuracy of spatial analysis within GIS environments, particularly for large-scale topographic mapping (1:10,000) and territorial recovery tasks in Ukraine. This study demonstrates that commonly used GIS approaches rely on simplified mathematical models that neglect the Earth's curvature, leading to reduced accuracy. To overcome these limitations, rigorous numerical methods based on computations on the reference ellipsoid (e.g., Karney's algorithms) are implemented and evaluated. The methodology combines analytical modelling in MATLAB with experimental validation in GIS software (QGIS, ArcGIS, MapInfo) using national and local datasets, including hydrographic networks. Results show a significant improvement in positional and metric accuracy, reaching near machine precision levels, and highlight key factors influencing error propagation in spatial analysis. The proposed approach supports the development of high-quality geospatial databases and enables more reliable spatial modelling for infrastructure planning, environmental monitoring, and post-conflict territorial recovery.

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1 Introduction

Today, most official and open geospatial datasets are produced by various providers using different methodologies, software and hardware tools, data models, and levels of automation. This leads to fragmentation of geoinformation products, varying quality, reduced timely updating of geospatial databases, and, as a result, difficulties in integrating such data. These consequences are also observed when working with geoinformation services of official government geoportals and VGA projects within a unified geoinformation environment. This is a typical situation during topographic mapping, the development of urban planning, scientific and design, and land management documentation, and the performance of hydrological and hydraulic engineering works.

During hydrological calculations for the design and construction of hydraulic structures, as well as during comprehensive hydrological studies, such as those conducted to analyse the water regime of a given area, the hydrographic characteristics of water bodies and their catchments are utilized.

The primary cartographic materials used to determine the hydrographic characteristics of water bodies and their catchments are topographic maps at scales of 1:10,000–1:100,000, as well as thematic maps (hydrographic, geological, soil, etc.). Prior to the modern development of geographic information systems and geospatial databases, cartometric operations in topographic mapping were performed directly on printed maps of the appropriate scale to determine morphometric characteristics, and geospatial objects that were longer or larger in area than the sheets of topographic maps occupied more than two

standard sheets, which necessitated the mandatory alignment and coordination of all objects along the boundaries, especially at the boundaries of zones in the Gauss-Krüger projection (Kin and Karpinskyi, 2021; Kin and Karpinskyi, 2024).

As a result of this cartographic approach, the scale of the map used affects the accuracy of determining hydrographic characteristics. In the second half of the 20th century, the use of large-scale maps to ensure high accuracy in determining hydrographic characteristics significantly increased the volume of cartometric work; therefore, small-scale maps were used in cases where high accuracy in determining characteristics was not required. Since the map scale affects the accuracy of determining hydrographic characteristics, the guidelines establish recommended scales for topographic maps depending on the size of the watersheds (Kin and Karpinskyi, 2024).

The modern development of geographic information systems and technologies allows for working with large volumes of data across extensive areas, that is, regardless of the size of topographic maps and the number of sheets required for calculating characteristics. The geographic information approach to map production involves modelling geospatial objects as continuous and non-fragmented entities. This allows for cartometric operations to be performed on the entire object, rather than its parts, and does not depend on the map scale, provided that the model of the geospatial object was not created by vectorizing scanned topographic maps.

The main objectives of the study include the following:

- To justify the use of rigorous numerical methods of cartometric, geodetic, and morphometric calculations on a reference ellipsoid.
- To develop and test functions for geodetic, cartometric, and morphometric calculations.
- To identify factors influencing the accuracy assessment of geodetic, cartometric, and morphometric calculations in a GIS environment.

The study covered the entire territory of Ukraine, and data sets were also analysed at the local level for the city of Vinnytsia.

2 Materials and Method

2.1 Method

The research methodology consisted of three stages:

1. determining reference values for cartometric operations in the MATLAB Online environment: a brief overview of formulas, justification of formula selection, accuracy of formulas, programming of

selected formulas, and documentation of the script for performing cartometric operations;

2. conducting experiments in a GIS environment: description of source data and coordinate systems, input of a point array, transformation of point coordinates, export of coordinate transformation results, documentation of the experiment execution scenario;
3. analysis of the experimental results: statistical analysis of the results, determination of distortion values on the Gauss-Krüger projection, sphere, and Krasovsky ellipsoid.

In exploring the capabilities of standard GIS tools, the following principle was adhered to: modern computer technologies enable the implementation of highly accurate, rigorous mathematical methods, which led to the determination of cartometric characteristics not on printed maps, but through geoinformation modelling.

The results of the study, obtained after analysing the datasets at the national level, were also tested at the local level.

2.2 Data Types and Collection

At the national level, the study examined official geospatial data from the topographic database of the Main State Topographic Map at a scale of 1:50,000 (2019) and data from the State Water Cadastre.

The official geospatial datasets and open data sources at the local level were used as input data and reference materials, such as: orthophotomap of Vinnytsia, scale 1:2000 (2019); topographic plan of Vinnytsia, scale 1:2000 (2013); river Basin Management Plan of the Southern Bug for 2025–2030; thematic cartographic schemes provided by the NGO «Small Rivers of Vinnytsia»; approved Concept for the Development of Small Rivers until 2035; Emerald Network data; local urban planning documentation; historical cartographic materials; OpenStreetMap data.

2.3 Data and Software Availability

A study was conducted of existing and newly developed functions for geodetic, cartometric, and morphometric calculations (Panou and Korakitis, 2021; Pérez et al, 2022; Kin and Karpinskyi, 2024) in the software tools MATLAB Online, MapInfo 11.0, QGIS 3.28, ArcGIS for Desktop 10.5, and Digitals. It was established that the implemented functions based on the Karney method (Karney, 2011; Karney, 2013; Karney, 2023) ensure high calculation accuracy on the reference ellipsoid and reduce the root mean square error to only the error of machine calculation and rounding, since the method under consideration uses the extended Kruger series, where the

terms of the series of functions are defined up to the 30th order. This allows for the determination of the metric properties of objects with nanometer-level accuracy, taking into account the curvature of the Earth.

The convergence of the results obtained by several methods allowed us to conclude that they are highly reliable (Table 1).

The developed Toolbox of geodetic and cartometric methods, including the data and code used in the provided examples and exercises, are published under a permissive CC-BY 4.0 license and available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10801557>.

All datasets obtained and processed in the project «Mapping Small Rivers in the Vinnytsia Community» are published under a permissive CC-BY 4.0 license and available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17816428>.

3 Results

3.1 Analysis of a nationwide dataset

To evaluate the accuracy of analytical and numerical methods for geodetic, cartometric, and morphometric calculations in a GIS environment, the following factors should be considered:

- 1) the positional accuracy of object vertices (m_1);
- 2) accuracy of the geospatial data collection method (m_2);
- 3) specified accuracy of the object's contour approximation (m_3);
- 4) accuracy of the analytical and numerical calculation method (m_4);
- 5) graphical scale accuracy (m_5);

It is recommended to consider the graphical scale accuracy if the objects were vectorized from topographic maps in a geographic information system. If an object was created based on the results of collected and processed geospatial data using a specific modern topographic surveying method, then the first 4 factors should be considered.

Figure 1 shows a graph of the relationship between the root-mean-square error of calculation on the reference ellipsoid and the length of the object and its resolution, specifically the number of points per 1 km or per 1 m.

The graph also shows that the longest river, the Dnieper, has the largest error, which is explained by the small number of points in the linear model of the river's flow; that is, the discretization of the object's vector model must be increased to improve the accuracy of determining the river's length.

Table 1. River lengths determined using the QGIS geoinformation system.

#	River Name	Length within Ukraine, km	Number of vertices in the line	Object length (Karney method), m	Object length (length(), QGIS), m
1	Dnipro	1155,71	1684	1152951,964	1152932,540
2	Southern Bug	849,029	33441	848300,109	848300,109
3	Horyn	638,819	23419	638802,311	638791,587
4	Western Bug	424,442	38874	424221,678	424214,535
5	Vorskla	380,983	7497	380750,306	380743,881
6	Ros	379,225	8174	378568,935	378562,559
7	Prut	276,954	4085	276898,423	276893,761
8	Danube	176,907	1766	176852,414	176849,430
9	Udy	161,641	4917	159932,785	159930,090
10	Oskol	160,258	1595	159000,783	158998,097
11	Uzh	86,044	1942	87746,182	87744,700
12	Merefa	29,1869	999	29037,745	29037,255
13	Mshanets	13,7653	489	13605,129	13604,900
14	Lyubotynka	12,012	114	11951,136	11951,000

A third-degree polynomial function was chosen only for this case. If we consider rivers ranging in length from 11 km to 900 km, the root-mean-square error of the calculation will be 5 cm per 1 km.

3.2 Analysis of local datasets

The lack of a unified geospatial database made it impossible to assess the extent of coastal degradation and plan for their restoration (Hopkins et al., 2025). It was precisely this gap that necessitated the creation of a geographic information system (GIS) for the small rivers of Vinnytsia – as a tool for recording, monitoring, and integrating aquatic ecosystems into urban planning. During the development of this geodatabase, rigorous numerical methods for determining the morphometric characteristics of rivers were employed.

Before integrating the datasets into a seamless geospatial database, the volunteer data was filtered and unified, as the valuable information was the identification of features and their detailed description. When river data were available in multiple datasets simultaneously, the features' geometries were harmonised to the official topographic plan at a scale of 1:2000, and the attribute data were refined using volunteer data and, in some cases,

OpenStreetMap data. A group of 30 volunteers also identified several new segments of watercourses that had not been documented and incorporated them into the hydrographic network model.

The results of the study made it possible, for the first time, to create a comprehensive geoinformation database on the small rivers of the Vinnytsia City Territorial Community. The total length of the river network, including the section of the Southern Bug within the city limits (approximately 13–14 km), is 167.48 km, of which 22.67 km are in culverts, while 144.81 km remain open.

4 Conclusion

The use of QGIS tools and the object-oriented database management system PostgreSQL/PostGIS for performing morphometric calculations on the surface of a reference ellipsoid is justified, since these software tools implement the Karney method. MapInfo 11.0, ArcGIS for Desktop 10.5, and Digitals do not perform calculations on the reference ellipsoid; instead, they use cartographic projections and a spherical model (in MapInfo), which does not ensure the accurate execution of these operations

Figure 1. Graph showing the relationship between the root-mean-square error of the Karney method and the length of the object.

and depends on distances to the central meridian, map scale, and projection distortions.

The function for determining the length of a watercourse ($ST_Length(geometry, true)$) calculates with an accuracy of 0.0005 mm, which is 1,000 times greater than the maximum accuracy of instrumental methods. The accuracy of geodetic area calculation using the Simpson and Karney methods increases by a factor of 10,000, from a cartographic error of m^2 per $1 m^2$ to a root-mean-square error of m^2 per $1 m^2$ when calculated using the geoinformation method.

The accuracy of computational operations has been improved by accounting for the Earth's curvature in the relevant fields of activity, which will enhance the quality of geospatial object tracking and monitoring, facilitate the integration and geospatial analysis of heterogeneous data, and improve the quality of geospatial data, such as coordinate-topological consistency.

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